

Internet Cafes in San Jose de Buenavista, Antique: Resources and Services

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Abstract

This study was conducted to determine the profile, resources, and services by the internet cafés in San Jose de Buenavista, Antique. A sample of five (5) internet cafés from the different barangays of the said municipality participated in this study. The internet café business in the said municipality started in 2007. The initial capital ranges from 100,000 to 500,000 pesos. Workers of internet cafés are expected to possess the following knowledge and skills: MS Office literacy, layouting in Photoshop, encoding, and troubleshooting. At least two (2) employees may realize such a business. The services offered by the internet cafés in San Jose de Buenavista, Antique include the following: gaming, surfing, downloading, emailing, CD burning, printing, photocopying, scanning, music editing, layouting, and consultancy.

Introduction

Information and communications technology (ICT) brings several benefits to different sectors. It benefits manufacturing, education, entertainment, and research among others. It ranges from a mere tool for day-to-day activities to a significant source of living. It provides additional opportunity for many people to venture into business.

Many businesses are associated with ICT. There are some businesses that produce ICT devices, sell ICT devices, and provide ICT services. Further, there are businesses that are said to be IT-enabled. Among these many IT businesses is the internet café.

An internet café or cybercafé is a place where one can use a computer with Internet access (Siegfredn, 2009). Internet cafés are located worldwide, and many people use them when traveling to access webmail and instant messaging services to keep in touch with family and friends (Wikipedia, 2013).

According to Austin (2007), the birth of the Internet dawned on March 1994 when the Philippine Network Foundation (PHNet), a consortium of private and government institutions, enabled the Filipinos to be connected live via a 64 kbps link to Sprint in the United States. It was then considered to be the country's only public gateway to the Internet. Prior to this, since 1986, the hobbyists operated the Bulletin Board Systems (BBS). It soon got connected and formed the local dial-up networks. This served as the vehicle for the development of cyberspace by exposing technically minded people to the possibilities and training them in netiquette and on-line way of life. Consequently, these systems got connected to international BBS networks, such as Fidonet. This allowed them to receive e-mail and download shareware programs and informational files. A year after its birth, in March 1995, the Public Telecommunications Act of the Philippines was signed into law. It removed the need for value-added service (VAS) providers to secure a franchise. This paved the way for many other organizations to establish connections to the

Internet, such as to create Web sites and having their own Internet services or providing Internet service and access to other groups and individuals.

Conceptual Framework

One of the researchers, who is a native of San Jose de Buenavista, Antique, observed that there are many, about 25, internet cafés in the town. It is because of this observation, the researchers found interest into examining the resources and services of those internet cafés in the town.

Figure 1 on the next page shows the conceptual framework of the study. The researchers believe that the internet cafés in San Jose de Buenavista, Antique operate with certain resources and offer certain services.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

Statement of the Problem

This research study determined the resources and services of the internet cafés in San Jose de Buenavista, Antique. Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the internet cafés in San Jose de Buenavista, Antique?
2. What are the resources of the internet cafés in San Jose de Buenavista, Antique for the business to operate?
3. What are the services offered by the internet cafés in San Jose de Buenavista, Antique?

Significance of the Study

The researcher considers the results of this study important to the IT students, businesspersons, schools, and government.

The IT students may get an idea of the knowledge and skills required to work in an internet café. The idea will help him or her anticipate the knowledge and skills requirements of other IT businesses.

The businesspersons may consider the results as bases should they intend to venture into internet café business. This may be a good reference in preparing a business plan.

The schools may consider the information in designing the curriculum. Teachers of business and IT subjects may also consider the information as a topic for discussion.

The government may get an idea of the job that may be available from internet cafés. This study may also provide information of the economic capabilities of Antique.

Scope and Limitations

This study was conducted during the second semester of the academic year 2012-2013. The sample from this study was the five (5) selected internet cafés in San Jose de Buenavista, Antique. The instrument used was designed by the researcher.

Methodology

This survey research aimed to determine the resources of the internet cafés to operate the business and the services they offer.

The instrument was made of three parts. The first part determines the basic profile of the internet café. This was designed to collect the following data: year started, initial capital, office space (rent or owned), age of the owner, sex of the owner, educational attainment of the owner, and marital status of the owner. The second part determines the resources of the internet café to operate the business. This was designed to collect the following data: number of employees, sex of the employees, knowledge and skills of the employees, and the facilities and equipment of the internet café. Lastly, the third part determines the services offered by the internet café.

Only five (5) of the internet cafés in the municipality of San Jose de Buenavista, Antique were involved in this study. A quota sampling method was employed, and the selection was based on the willingness to participate in this study.

Each authorized person of the selected internet cafés was given the instrument. After collecting the instrument duly supplied, the data were processed. The frequency, relative frequency, and mode were used to analyze the gathered data.

Results

Tables and texts below present the profile, resources, and services of the internet cafés in San Jose de Buenavista, Antique based on the sample.

Table 1 on the next page shows the profile of the internet cafés in San Jose de Buenavista, Antique. Their business started as early as 2007 and as late as 2012; most (60%) of them started between the years 2009 to 2010. The initial capital ranges from 100,000 to 500,000 pesos; most (40%) of them started with a capital of between 400,001 to 500,000 pesos. The office space is either rented or owned; most (80%) of them are rented. The owner's age ranges from 26 to 65 years old; most (60%) of the owners age between 26 to 35 years old. Most (80%) of the owners are male. All (100%) of them are Bachelor's degree holder. The marital status of the owners is either single or married; most (80%) of them are married.

Table 1
Profile of the Internet Cafés in San Jose de Buenavista, Antique

Category	f	%
Year Started		
2011-2012	1	20
2009-2010	3	60
2007-2008	1	20
Initial Capital		
400,001-500,000	2	40
300,001-400,000	1	20
200,001-300,000	1	20
100,000-200,000	1	20
Office Space		
Rented	4	80
Owned	1	20
Owner's Age		
56-65	1	20
46-55	0	0
36-45	1	20
26-35	3	60
Owner's Sex		
Male	4	80
Female	1	20
Owner's Ed. Attainment		
BS graduate	5	100
Owner's Marital Status		
Single	1	20
Married	4	80

Table 2 on the next page shows the manpower resources of the internet cafés in San Jose de Buenavista, Antique. The number of employees ranges from two (2) to four (4); most (40%) of them have two or three employees. Most (64%) of the employees are male. In terms of the knowledge and skills of their employees, they possess the following: MS Office literacy, layouting in Photoshop, encoding, and troubleshooting. The internet cafés have the following facilities and equipment: computer units with webcam and headset, scanner, printer, photocopier, router, switch, UTP cable, internet connection, tables, and chairs.

Table 2

Manpower Resource of the Internet Cafés in San Jose de Buenavista, Antique

Category	f	%
Number of Employees		
4	1	20
3	2	40
2	2	40
Employee's Sex		
Male	9	64
Female	5	36

The services offered by the internet cafés in San Jose de Buenavista, Antique include the following: gaming, surfing, downloading, emailing, CD burning, printing, photocopying, scanning, music editing, layouting, and consultancy.

Implications and Conclusions

The internet café business in San Jose de Buenavista, Antique started late since the earliest year such business started in the said municipality was in 2007. The initial capital to put-up an internet café business is considerable because 100,000 pesos may already realize such a business. It seems to suggest that renting an office space for the internet café is ideal.

Engaging into internet café business would only require a minimal number of employees, two employees may suffice. Knowledge and skills required to work in an internet café are only limited. Such skills may be gained even by taking short-term courses.

Like in other places, internet cafés in San Jose de Buenavista, Antique offer similar services.

Recommendations

Business-minded persons of any age and of any course may consider engaging into internet café business. Realizing such a business requires minimal resources.

Persons who would like to work in an internet café do not really need to complete a Bachelor's degree in information technology. Short-term courses in computer operations and troubleshooting may suffice. Working in an internet café requires only minimal knowledge and skills.

Owners of internet cafés in San Jose de Buenavista, Antique may consider other services to include in their business to maximize the revenue.

References

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